

The Quaternary Alkaloids of *Cocculus laurifolius* DC*

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The quaternary aporphine alkaloids, laurifoline and magnoflorine chlorides and O-methylisocorydine, isocorydine and boldine methochlorides have been isolated from the water soluble alkaloidal fraction of *Cocculus laurifolius* DC. These quaternary aporphine bases have been found to be responsible for neuromuscular blocking and hypotensive activities of the water soluble alkaloidal fraction of the plant.

COCCLUSUS laurifolius DC (Menispermaceae) an evergreen shrub which grows in tropical and subtropical region of the world, has been a rich source of 1-benzylisoquinoline derived alkaloids¹⁻³. Our interest in the alkaloidal constituents of *C. laurifolius* arose when hypotensive and neuromuscular blocking activities⁴ were found to be concentrated in the alkaloidal fraction of the ethanolic extract of the plant. A number of abnormal *Erythrina*⁵⁻¹⁰, dibenz-(d, f) azonine¹¹ and morphinandienone¹² alkaloids have been isolated by us earlier from the plant. We now report the isolation and characterization of quaternary aporphine alkaloids responsible for hypotensive and neuromuscular blocking activities in the water soluble alkaloidal fraction of the leaves of *C. laurifolius*.

The quaternary bases were isolated as chloride salts by reinckate method¹³. The mixture of quaternary bases by careful chromatography on silica gel and cellulose and preparative thin layer chromatography gave the following bases. Alkaloid A (C₂₀H₂₄O₄NCl) m.p. 253° (decomp); alkaloid B (C₂₀H₂₄O₄NCl) m.p. 202-203° (decomp); alkaloid C (C₂₂H₂₈O₄NCl) m.p. 228-230° (decomp); alkaloid D (C₂₁H₂₀O₄NCl) m.p. 232-235° (decomp) and alkaloid E (C₂₀H₂₄O₄NCl) m.p. 242-255° (decomp).

The IR spectrum of alkaloid A ($\nu_{\max}$: 3380, 1604 and 1240 cm⁻¹) in conjunction with its UV data ($\lambda_{\max}$: 227, 281 and 307 nm and $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 315 nm) suggested the presence of 1,2,9 and 10 tetrasubstituted aporphine system¹⁴. In the NMR spectrum a six proton singlet at τ 6.12 was due to C-2 and C-10 methoxyl groups. The aromatic region of the spectrum had three protons. Of these, one proton singlet at τ 2.2 was due to C-11 aromatic proton. This confirmed the presence of 1,2,9,10 tetrasubstituted aporphine system in the base¹⁵. The aromatic protons at C-3 and C-8 resonated at τ 3.2 and 3.0 respectively. A six proton singlet at τ 6.8 was assigned to N(CH₃)₂ group. The structure (1) of laurifoline chloride¹⁶ emerged for alkaloid A from the data presented above. Direct comparison (TLC and Co-TLC) established the identity.

The IR ($\nu_{\max}$: 3380, 1605 and 1235 cm⁻¹) and UV ($\lambda_{\max}$: 225, 273 and 310 nm and $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 330 nm) spectra of alkaloid B suggested that alkaloid B is a representative of 1,2,10 and 11-tetrasubstituted aporphine alkaloids¹⁴. This was confirmed by its NMR spectrum. In the NMR spectrum of the base the aromatic methoxyl groups at C-2 and C-10 appeared as a singlet at τ 6.23. Of the three aromatic protons the proton at C-3 appeared as a singlet at τ 3.15. The remaining two aromatic protons at C-8 and C-9 resonated together at τ 2.92. A six proton singlet at τ 6.75 was assigned to N⁺(Me)₂ group. The data presented above suggested that the alkaloid B had the structure (3) of magnoflorine chloride¹⁷. Direct comparison (TLC and Co-TLC) established the identity.

- (1) R=H, R₁=Me
(2) R=Me, R₁=H

- (3) R=R₁=H
(4) R=R₁=Me
(5) R=Me, R₁=H

The IR ($\nu_{\max}$: 1603 and 1235 cm⁻¹) and UV ($\lambda_{\max}$: 220, 270 and 300 nm) spectra of alkaloid C were suggestive of the presence of 1,2,10 and 11-tetrasubstituted aporphine system¹⁴. In the NMR spectrum of the base a sharp singlet for six protons at τ 6.23 was due to methoxyl groups at C-2 and C-10. A singlet for three protons at τ 6.52 was assigned to methoxy group at C-1. A singlet for three protons at τ 6.3 was due to methoxyl group at C-11. In aromatic region one proton singlet at τ 3.2 was assigned to C-3 proton. The aromatic protons at C-8 and C-9 resonated at τ 2.70 and 2.80 respectively as an AB quartet, (J_{AB}=9.0 Hz) which clearly suggested that the methoxyl groups are at

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the adjacent positions C-10 and C-11. Two sharp singlets each of three protons at τ 6.72 and 6.81 were due to $\overset{+}{N}(\text{Me})_2$ group. The structure (4) of O-methylisocorydinemethochloride¹⁸ emerged for alkaloid C from the data given above. Direct comparison (TLC and Co-TLC) with an authentic sample prepared from isocorydine¹⁸ established the identity.

The IR (ν_{max} : 3180, 1600 and 1230 cm^{-1}) and UV (λ_{max} : 220, 268 and 300 nm and $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH-NaOH}}$ 330 nm) spectra of alkaloid D suggested that the base had 1,2,10 and 11-tetrasubstituted aporphine system¹⁴. In the NMR spectrum of the base a singlet for six protons at τ 6.2 was due to methoxyl groups at C-2 and C-10. A three protons singlet at τ 6.4 was assigned to methoxyl group at C-1. In the aromatic region one proton singlet at τ 3.1 was assigned to C-3 proton. The protons at C-8 and C-9 resonated at τ 2.88 as a broad singlet. The three protons singlets at τ 6.7 and 6.78 were due to $\overset{+}{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ group. The data presented above suggested that alkaloid D has the structure (5) of isocorydine methochlorides¹⁹. Direct comparison (TLC and Co-TLC) with an authentic sample prepared from isocorydine established the identity.

The IR (ν_{max} 3382, 1603 and 1238 cm^{-1}) and UV (λ_{max} 220, 280 and 305 nm and $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH-NaOH}}$ 315 nm) spectra of alkaloid E suggested the presence of 1,2,9 and 10-tetrasubstituted aporphine system in the base¹⁴. In the NMR spectrum of the base the three protons singlet at τ 6.5 and τ 6.2 were assigned to methoxyl groups at C-1 and C-10. In the aromatic region one proton singlet at τ 2.3 was assigned to C-11 proton. The singlets at τ 3.1 and τ 2.9 were due to protons at C-3 and C-8 respectively. Three proton singlets at τ 6.8 and τ 6.9 were due to $\overset{+}{N}(\text{Me})_2$ group. The structure (2) of boldine methochloride emerged for alkaloid E from the data given above.

Biological Activity :

Alkaloid A, alkaloid B, alkaloid C, alkaloid D and alkaloid E isolated from the leaves of *C. laurifolius* are found to have *d*-tubocurarine like curarizing actions on the sciatic skeletal muscles. While the hypotensive activity of laurifoline chloride²⁰ (Alkaloid A) is known, the other alkaloids also induced hypotensive effects in dog, cat and rabbit. The hypotensive response of the animals to these alkaloids almost corresponded to the response to hexamethonium iodide, but duration of action is shorter. This activity was due to considerable ganglionic blocking actions on the various sympathetic and *para*-sympathetic ganglia.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer 157 grating infracord. UV spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 202 automatic recording spectrophotometer. The NMR spectra were taken in

varian A-60D spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal reference and the chemical shift values are expressed in τ units.

Extraction :

The leaves of *Cocculus laurifolius* DC (menispermaceae) for the present investigation were collected in September from Dehradun. The air dried leaves (20 kg) were pulverized and extracted with EtOH (4×40) by cold percolation. The solvent from the combined percolate was removed under reduced pressure below 40°. The dark green viscous mass (2.0 kg), so obtained, was extracted with 5% AcOH (6×400 ml). The combined aqueous acidic solution was defatted with petroleum ether, basified with Na_2CO_3 (pH 9) and the liberated bases were extracted with CHCl_3 .

Isolation of Quaternary Bases :

The aqueous basic solution after removal of secondary and tertiary alkaloids was acidified with 5% AcOH (pH 2) and to it was added neutral solution of ammonium reineckate till the precipitation was complete. The red coloured precipitate, so obtained, was filtered off, washed with H_2O and dried (anhyd. P_2O_5). The complex (34 g) was extracted with acetone (6×200 ml) to give acetone soluble and acetone insoluble fractions. The acetone soluble fraction was passed through a column of neutral Al_2O_3 (120 g). The combined eluate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give reddish brown viscous mass (21 g) which was taken in water (400 ml) and warmed to 50-60°. To it was added Ag_2SO_4 (5.8 g) in warm water (140 ml) in three portions during 3 h with vigorous stirring and finally BaCl_2 (4.7 g) in water (100 ml) was added to it. The resulting mixture was kept overnight and filtered. The filtrate was again treated with BaCl_2 to remove completely excess of Ag_2SO_4 . Evaporation of water from the filtrate *in vacuo* below 50° yielded the water-soluble bases (10 g) as chlorides.

Isolation of Bases :

The mixture of quaternary base chlorides (10 g) was carefully chromatographed over a column of SiO_2 (1

TABLE 1

FrNO :	Eluant	Weight (g)	Remarks
69-78	CHCl_3 : MeOH (90:10)	0.12	Alkaloid A
79-85	(85:15)	0.25	Complex mix.
86-95	(80:20)	0.14	Alkaloid B
96-105	(75:25)	0.12	Alkaloid C
106-120	(60:40)	1.6	Mixture of two alkaloids (D+E)
121-150	(40:60)	2.1	Complex mixture.

kg). The column was eluted with hexane, hexane : C_6H_6 (1:1), C_6H_6 , C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (1:1), $CHCl_3$ and $CHCl_3$: MeOH with increasing proportion of the polar solvent. Elution was monitored by TLC. A total of 150 fractions, each of 250 ml were collected and mixed on TLC basis. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Alkaloid A :

The fractions 69-78, single spot on SiO_2 plates (solvent: MeOH), were mixed, the solvent removed and the residue crystallized from MeOH: Et_2O to give alkaloid A (0.082 g) m.p. 253° (decomp) $[\alpha]_D^{25} +26.3^\circ$; ν_{max} : 3380, 2900, 2550, 1600, 1560, 1470, 1450, 1400, 1240, 1110 and 870 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} : 227, 281 and 307 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 227, 290 and 315 nm; NMR (D_2O): τ 6.12 (S, 6H, C_2-OCH_3 and $C_{10}-OCH_3$), 2.2 (S, 1H, $C_{11}-H$), 3.2 (S, 1H, C_3-H), 3.0 (S, 1H, C_8-H), 6.8 (S, 6H, $N-(CH_2)_2$), 7.5-7.8 (m, 7H, benzylic-H).

Alkaloid A was found identical (TLC and Co-TLC) with laurifoline chloride (lit¹⁸ m.p. 254°).

Alkaloid B :

The fractions 86-95, single spot on SiO_2 plates (solvent: MeOH) were mixed, the solvent removed and the residue was crystallized from MeOH: Et_2O to give alkaloid B (0.05 g) m.p. 202-203° (decomp); base iodide m.p. 248-249° (decomp); ν_{max} : 3380, 2880, 2540, 1605, 1550, 1450, 1403, 1235, 1110 and 920 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 225, 273 and 310 nm and λ_{max} 226, 276 and 330 nm; NMR (D_2O): τ 6.23 (S, 6H, C_2-OCH_3 and $C_{10}-OCH_3$), 3.15 (S, 1H, C_3-H), 2.92 (bs, 2H, C_8-H and C_9-H), 6.75 (bs, 6H, $N-(CH_2)_2$), 7.5-7.8 (m, 7H, benzylic-H).

Alkaloid B was found identical (TLC and Co-TLC) with magnoflorine chloride (lit¹⁷ m.p. 202-203; base iodide m.p. 248-249°).

Alkaloid C :

The fractions 96-105, single spot on SiO_2 plates (solvent: MeOH) were mixed, the solvent removed and the residue was crystallized from MeOH: Et_2O to give alkaloid C, m.p. 228-230° (decomp); base iodide, m.p. 220-223°; ν_{max} : 2900, 2500, 1603, 1550, 1450, 1400, 1235, 1120 and 980 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} : 220, 270 and 300 nm; NMR (D_2O): τ 6.23 (S, 6H, C_2-OCH_3 and $C_{10}-OCH_3$) 6.52 (S, 3H, C_1-OCH_3), 6.3 (S, 3H, $C_{11}-OCH_3$) 3.2 (S, 1H, C_3-H), 2.7 and 2.82 (q, 2H, J AB=9.0 Hz, C_8-H and C_9-H), 6.72 and 6.81 (2S, 6H, $N-(CH_2)_2$) 7.6-7.8 (m, 7H, benzylic-H)

Alkaloid C was found identical (UV, IR, Co-TLC) with an authentic sample of O-methylisocorydine methochloride prepared from isocorydine¹⁸.

Alkaloids D and E :

The solvent from fractions 106-120 was removed and the residue (1.6 g) was carefully rechromatographed over a column of cellulose (60 g). The column was eluted with Et_2O : MeCOEt (1:7) saturated with 1% aqueous HCl.

The fractions 51-60, single spot on SiO_2 plate (solvent: MeOH) were mixed, the solvent removed and the residue was crystallized from MeOH: Et_2O to give alkaloid D (0.082 g) m.p. 232-35° (decomp); $[\alpha]_D^{25} +162.3^\circ$ (H_2O); base iodide m.p. 224-226° (decomp); ν_{max} : 3180, 2900, 2530, 1600, 1550, 1460, 1230, 1110 and 850 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} : 220, 268 and 300 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 226 and 342 nm; NMR (D_2O): τ 6.2 (S, 6H, C_2-OCH_3 and $C_{10}-OCH_3$), 6.4 (S, 3H, C_1-OCH_3), 3.1 (S, 1H, C_3-H), 2.88 (bs, 2H, C_8-H and C_9-H), 6.7 and 6.78 (2S, 6H, $N-(CH_2)_2$), 7.5-7.8 (m, 7H, benzylic-H)

Alkaloid E :

The fractions 73-88, single spot on SiO_2 plate (solvent: MeOH) were mixed, the solvent removed and the residue crystallized from MeOH: Et_2O to give alkaloid E (0.038 g), m.p. 252-255° (decomp); ν_{max} : 2850, 2520, 1603, 1560, 1455, 1403, 1238, and 870 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOH}$ 228, 289 and 315 nm; NMR (D_2O): τ 6.5 (S, 3H, C_1-OCH_3), 6.2 (S, 3H, $C_{10}-OCH_3$) 2.3 (S, 1H, $C_{11}-H$), 3.1 (S, 1H, C_3-H), 2.9 (S, 1H, C_8-H), 6.8 and 6.9 (2S, 6H, $N-(CH_2)_2$), 7.5-7.8 (m, 7H, benzylic-H).

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